

**COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING
THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE****Kibriyokhon Muzaffarjon kizi Solijonova**

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the competency-based approach in teaching the Russian language within the context of modern educational reforms. It focuses on the development of key competences, particularly linguistic and communicative competences, as essential outcomes of higher education. The study analyzes the theoretical foundations of the concepts of competence and competency, drawing on the works of leading scholars, and highlights their practical orientation in language teaching. Special attention is paid to the distinction between linguistic competence and language competence, as well as their role in the formation of effective speech activity.

The modernization of the education system in our country has set the development of key competences – namely, the formation of a competency-based approach in teaching – as a primary goal for pedagogical higher education institutions. Consequently, in the process of improving modern education, there is a growing tendency to gradually shift from a traditional approach to a competency-based one. Within this shift, the educational process is no longer based solely on the formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities, but also on the development of students' competences. This has led to the emergence of new conceptual and methodological foundations and models for training specialists.

Before emphasizing the advantages of the competency-based approach in education, particularly in teaching the Russian language, it is necessary to understand the essence of the concepts of *competence*, *competency*, and the *competency-based approach*.

The term *competence* was first introduced in scientific research by Noam Chomsky, a theoretical linguist whose theory of universal grammar significantly influenced the field of linguistics. He used this term to denote the ability to produce speech, contrasting it with the concept of *performance*. The scholar argued that competence is the ability to produce and understand a sufficient number of grammatically correct utterances, based on the linguistic signs acquired by an individual and the rules governing their combination. Accordingly, performance was understood as the actual process of producing and comprehending speech.

Expanding on this idea, Z. F. Yusupova emphasizes that competence is also a set of interrelated fundamental personal qualities, including the application of knowledge, skills, and abilities in productive activity [1].

In analyzing the concept of competence in the interpretations of I. A. Zimnyaya, a strong orientation toward practical human activity becomes evident.

A revolutionary step in language teaching was the introduction of the concept of *communicative competence* by the American sociolinguist Dell Hymes, who argued that speech communication is carried out not only through linguistic signs and the rules of their combination but also through knowledge of cultural and socially significant contexts. This contributed to the widespread use of the term *competence* [2].

The main goal of teaching foreign languages is the development of linguistic competences among future philologists in accordance with their professional profile. Language competence is considered not only an educational outcome but also an integral socio-personal and behavioral phenomenon.

In their scholarly works, I. L. Kolesnikova and O. A. Dolgina argue that vocabulary units and grammatical rules, which transform lexical items into meaningful expressions, constitute language competence [3]. At the same time, in the dictionary *Culture of Speech Communication: Ethics. Pragmatics. Psychology* [4], this term is defined as “a good knowledge of the system of a given language, its phonetic units and laws, vocabulary, grammatical forms and patterns, styles, and stylistic means.” It is also noted that the sufficiency or insufficiency of language competence is one of the indicators determining the level of speech skills. However, these definitions may be considered somewhat vague, as they are closely associated with the concept of “knowledge” in the traditional KSA (knowledge, skills, abilities) system, which, as is well known, cannot guarantee successful communication.

In the *Dictionary of Linguistic Terms*, the concept of *language competence*, in addition to the definitions mentioned above, includes the necessity of mastering communicative skills that enable a speaker to understand contexts of varying complexity and effectively carry out speech-thinking activity.

In her works, E. D. Bozhovich notes that, according to Chomsky, this term is semantically opposed to the concept of *language use*. The key distinction lies in the difference between the speaker-listener’s knowledge of the language and the correct use of the language in communication and human activity. Over time, followers of the scholar began to replace these terms with *language ability* and *language activity*, where the former refers to the potential knowledge of language possessed by a native speaker, and the latter refers to actual speech in real conditions [5]. In the book *Psycholinguistics* by D. Slobin and J. Green, *language ability* is defined as what a person is theoretically capable of saying and understanding, while *language activity* refers to what a person actually says and understands in specific situations [6].

The distinction between *linguistic competence* and *language competence* is clearly presented in the lecture notes of Z. F. Yusupova. According to her, linguistic competence involves basic knowledge of linguistics, including all information related to Russian studies and the understanding of the Russian language as a social phenomenon. In contrast, language competence refers to knowledge of the language itself and its norms, which ensure not only comprehension of others’ speech and production of one’s own speech but also orthographic and punctuation accuracy [7].

The level of language competence is assessed, firstly, by knowledge of the rules of the language being studied, and secondly, by the ability to understand and reproduce speech. A

number of scholars (E. M. Vereshchagin, V. G. Kostomarov [8], S. Moirand [9], S. Savignon [10], L. F. Bachman [11], Jan van Ek [12], M. N. Vyatyutnev [13], G. V. Kolshansky [14], and others) argue that the formation of language competence alone cannot ensure productive speech practice. For this purpose, it is necessary to simultaneously expand knowledge of the structure and systemic nature of the language, as well as develop the ability to apply this system in practice.

If, in the process of forming language competence, priority is given to the development of the student's personality, then their educational language skills and abilities are considered within the framework of linguistic competence. Linguistic competence includes the development of three types of skills:

- **recognition skills** (the ability to distinguish one linguistic phenomenon from another),
- **classification skills** (the ability to group linguistic phenomena),
- **analytical skills** (the ability to perform phonetic, morphemic, word-formation, morphological, syntactic, and stylistic analysis).

Linguistic competence should be understood as the result of students' comprehension of oral speech. "It includes knowledge of the fundamentals of the science of the Russian language and presupposes the mastery of a system of linguistic concepts. ... Linguistic competence also implies the formation of an understanding of how the Russian language is structured, what and how changes within it, which aspects are the most 'problematic,' as well as the assimilation of knowledge about the role of language in the life of society and the individual. On this basis, a stable interest in the subject, as well as respect and love for the native language, are developed," writes Z. F. Yusupova in her lecture notes, thereby highlighting the distinction between language competence and linguistic competence..

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